

AMALGAMATION SOCIOLOGY: THE BANE OF NIGERIA'S POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Eno, Reuben Enang Eno
reubeneno408@gmail.com
08162343994

ABSTRACT

The paper discusses Nigeria's development within the context of colonialism. The research is aimed at examining the negative effects of amalgamation policy of 1914 on the economic and political development of Nigeria. The paper argued that Nigeria's economic and political problems can be traced to the negative impact of indirect rule strategy which has accounted for the violent post-colonial politics leading to continued hindrance to the nation democracy and development since independence. The paper therefore concludes that, the injurious effects of amalgamation policy and its implications on ethnic conflicts inequality in revenue-allocation formula, religious division and civil war Vis-à-vis militancy and terrorism notwithstanding are contemporary issues affecting economic and political development in Nigeria till date.

KEYWORDS: Amalgamation, Political Economic Development, Ethnic Conflict, Religious Division and Revenue Allocation

INTRODUCTION

The ascendancy of Nigeria as a nation can be traced to two different periods in history: The influx of colonialism and the amalgamation geography producing two protectorates by British imperialism. The oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary defined “amalgamation” as the joining of different constituent parts to form one large organization. Sociologically, it refers to a sociological process by which two different cultures blend together and a new culture originates. In other words, it is a process of bringing together of people from different ethnic, religious and cultural background or nationality into one administrative political authority in order to achieve or promote collective conscience, morality and collective representation as a group. The 1914 amalgamation in Nigeria which produced the northern and southern protectorates which were previously administered as separate through related territories is generally regarded as the birth date of the Nigerian State (Egbosa, 2022). Paradoxically, the amalgamation policy of 1914 by British colonialists was not for the interest and development of Nigeria, rather it helps to galvanize the exploitation of Nigeria's economic resources and also to strengthen a coercive economic administration (Egbulem. 2010) In effect, the 1914 amalgamation in Nigeria destroyed an indigenous political and administrative system that was far from more democratic and accountable and replaced it with a colonial system of government that was wholly undemocratic and lacked any kind of accountability. A corollary of this gave birth to the creation of northern, southern and eastern regions with attendant wide

range devastating consequences that has hindered economic and political development of the nation till date. Consequent upon the foregoing, one major democratic problems of Nigeria during post-colonial to independence period with grave consequence on economic and political development is the uneven approach giving to derivation formula for the sharing of federally collected revenue based on 65% within the three federating regions now states between 1952 to 1954 which was not favourably to eastern region and a host of other problems that will be discussed in the later part of this paper, points to amalgamation drama in Nigeria.

In reference to economic and political development, Annana (2006) did make the point that, economic development suggests qualitative change and the creation of new economic and non-economic structures which increase the quality of life of the citizenry through proper fiscal arrangements between the levels of government in a federation and each of the levels of government will be developed economically and lives of the citizens will be transformed. In real sense, economic development denote a situation where the basic need of individuals of health, education, food, water, sanitation and housing are provided by the state.

On the other hand, political development refers to the development of the institutions, attitudes, and values that form the political power system of a society (Burnell, 2011). As Park observed in 1984 that, the values to be developed are in terms of the capacity of the political system to satisfy the changing needs of members of the society. From the foregoing assertion, it must be deduced that economic and political development are like Siamese twins in the context of development and governance in Nigeria. This is because the both concepts is basically concern with the idea of meeting the needs of members of the society by enhancing the standard of living. However, it is against this background that this research paper seeks to examine the effects of amalgamation on Nigeria's political and economic development. Structurally, the paper is divided into two main parts. Part one places basic concepts in their correct perspectives. Part two situates the effects of amalgamation Policy on economic and political development of Nigeria. This is followed by summary and conclusion.

CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE

Amalgamation: The Nigeria Perspective

The evolution of Nigeria as a nation is a direct result of the 1914 amalgamation policy which British colonialism introduced. During this period the Northern and Southern protectorates was merged to form what is now known as Nigeria. The colonial administration and imperial occupations carved up boundaries that divided territories inhabited by indigenous societies and brought together a diversity of ethnic communities within unitary administrative structures. According to Ebegbulem (2010) in Nigeria, between 1914 to 1915 British colonial administrators created three unequal territories that explain “ethno-genesis” and later “ethno-tension”; thus the North became Hausa/Fulani and the West inhabited by Yoruba while the East occupied by Ibos. In fact within these divisive colonial structure ethnic tensions emerged between these unequally developed groups. Commenting further, Dare in 1986 observed that, the administrative structure that followed the amalgamation policy also introduced a contradictory administrative system through the operation of the so called “Indirect rule” policy which continued to treat the various units as separate entities and allowed each to develop in whatever direction it choses in isolation from the others. Again as I have occasion to point out in the introductory chapter, that economic determinism warranted

the amalgamation of the two protectorates in Nigeria (North and south). It is argued in some quarters that before 1914 the Northern protectorate would not find sufficient funds to maintain its own administrative structure rather the financial position of the southern protectorate was encouraging because of its vast sea ports, as such the economic resources in the southern protectorate were utilized to oil the development of both Northern and southern protectorates through amalgamation. This policy was carried out for selfish interest of the colonial government. Essentially, the amalgamation principle came into the political dictionary of Nigeria through the personal interest or ambition of Lord Lugard. It was argued that the main reasons were to secure firm control over the southern protectorate as he had done in the North and to extend the policies he had introduced in the Northern protectorate to the south. Reacting further, Gana and Egwu (2003) asserts that the 1914 amalgamation principle established a system of indirect rule that was based on a policy of non-centralized administration. Theoretically, indirect rule meant the utilization of existing traditional administrative structures for governing and also allowing each ethnic group to develop along its own lines. What this meant in practice was that; the traditional rulers were located and empowered to govern their respective domains as before. Where no paramount leaders were known to exist in the traditional setup, warrant chiefs were appointed. It was these warrant chiefs that governed in most parts of the East with varying degrees of success.

The upshot of amalgamation were numerous in the Nigerian body politics and contemporary crisis which are the outcome of a number of forces reflective of colonial indirect rule whose interactions have pushed the nation down a particular path and has exacerbated ethnicity, regionalism, religious division, uneven derivation policy and lopsided fiscal federalism implementation thus making it difficult to achieve any meaningful political and economic development in Nigeria after independence.

THE EFFECTS OF AMALGAMATION POLICY ON NIGERIA'S ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT

Inequality in Revenue Allocation Formula

It is clearly evident that one of the problems affecting Nigerian's economic and political development is the direct result of the struggle between the three ethnic regions over the control of the national wealth and power at the centre. This phenomenon has made Nigeria's politics rather volatile. More so, the pressure that was put on the then colonial government by the different regions arising from the unequal contribution of all economic areas to the national wealth led to the evolution of revenue allocation formula in Nigeria. In post-colonial to Independence era, it was argued that between 1954 to 1959, the colonial government establish an autonomous revenue and tax jurisdiction policy to the regional governments based on the principle of derivation in the sharing of federally collected revenue. This formula created a lot of disparities within the three regions in terms of economic development. Consequently at different stages, the revenue allocation formula were adjusted and criteria between and within levels of governments in Nigeria. Nevertheless there appears to be a significant relationship between structural and power relations as regard to the distribution of revenue within the major ethnic groups which were the main contributors to the nation's wealth. Allocation of revenue was based on the average of 65%. One major distinguish

factor of these phases of revenue sharing formula was the much accorded emphasis on the derivation principle.

This revenue sharing formula distorted the economic and political development of Nigeria, because significant development projects were centred on regional level rather than national development. As observed by Egwaikhide and Isumoniah (2001) derivation formula pleased the northern and western regions considering the boom in their export commodities: cotton and groundnut in the North and Cocoa in the West. The Eastern region whose main export crop palm oil was facing difficult times in the global market was unhappy with the derivation policy because it affected the development of the Eastern region in all ramifications as compare to the other two regions (West and North) economically. When revenue allocation was based on derivation principle, the Northern and Western regions had various social and economic facilities including universities, banks, business outfits and chains of Hotel facilities to show for their regions resources while the case was different in the Eastern region. Another important issue worthy of note is the declaration of Chief Awolowo when he expresses the opinion that “in embracing western culture, the Yoruba take the lead and benefited by the regions wealth based on 65% derivation. This policy galvanized them into the great height in Nigeria's political economy. This however, was the genesis of fiscal imbalance and the agitation for equitable revenue sharing formula was given deaf ears because of the contending primordial interest between the northern and western region elites.

In reality, the derivation formula created a lot of inequalities within ethnic lines, and did not go well in Nigeria as a newly developing nation. The derivation policy did not only affect the economic and political development, but it also weakens the legitimacy of the central government in performing its responsibilities to the citizens. As a result, Nigeria's standard of living was undoubtedly affected mostly within the minority ethnic groups. The different phases of revenue allocation commissions in the post-colonial period notably of Phillipson assertion of 1946, Hicks position in 1951, Chicks assertion of 1958, and Barisman position of 1958 emphasized the derivation formula in revenue allocation. Besides these era points to the fact that: the much agitated revenue allocation formula of derivation which also includes resource control thus, its re-emphasises in contemporary times had almost, turned the nation ablaze. Ironically, it has been in practice during post-colonial and independence era without any complains because the North and West were the major beneficiaries of this derivation policy.

The foregoing factors puts the minority ethnic groups in contemporary times particularly the South-South region in a state of dilemma in considering why the North and the power configuration in the West are now rejecting restructuring of the Nigerian federation when resource control has been a common practice in the past. Finally for this section to be noted also is the fact that when Nigeria got her independence, there was a change in emphasis as regard to revenue allocation formula thus subsequent revenue allocation commissions were constituted notably: Aboyade in 1977, Okigbo in 1979 and National Revenue Mobilization Allocation and Fiscal commission in 1989 de-emphasized derivation policy. It was argued that, as a new independent state it was necessary for the federal government to have financial stability that will guarantee development in the regions; as a result the first two post-independence constitutions of 1960 to 1963 provided 50% derivation in respect to all revenues from minerals. Ironically, this was a deliberate attempt by the power configuration in Nigeria

because it was realized that crude oil was discovered in a neglected parts of Eastern region now known as South-South region.

More so, the pre-eminence accorded to crude oil globally cannot be compared to the political economy of agriculture that has sustained the northern and western regions in the past. Crude oil became the major source of Nigeria's economy. In other words, the assertion of Fashina in 1998 lends credence when he opined that the weight accorded to derivation principle appears to have been determined by the interest of the different factions of the ruling class and their political power. From the above assertion, it can be deduced that the discovery of crude oil in the minority region of South-South orchestrated the paradigm shift in revenue formula for sharing of federally, collected revenue to the different federating units to fiscal federalism because of primordial interest of self-acclaimed power blocs representing the north and west. In so far as the problems of Nigeria's economic and political development is seen to be associated with the imbalances created by the introduction of derivation policy which 1914 amalgamation nurtured, although conceived in the womb of colonialism, bedevilled the unity and progress of the nation in general. It is clearly evident that inequality in revenue allocation has in contemporary times created a lot of challenges between federal and state governments in considering which sharing formula is appropriate for the country because of 1914 amalgamation drama.

ETHNIC CONFLICTS

One central reason for the stunted democracy, economic and political development in Nigeria is the issue of ethnicity. The prevalence of ethnic conflicts in the nation is the direct effect of amalgamation policy of 1914, as mentioned before in the introductory chapter, the indiscriminate merger of various ethnic groups under one national umbrella and as it to contradict this effort, through the operation of the so called indirect rule policy which continued to treat the various units as separate entities and allowed each to develop in whatever ways it chose to in isolation to others. Besides since the various ethnic groups that formed what is now known as Nigeria were not consulted before the merger resulted to ethnic differences and conflicts among them at every point in contact.

In contemporary Nigeria society, ethnicity has been widely recognised as a central factor contributing to political problems. Balewa in 1994 aptly observed that probably the most important and sinister factor in Nigeria's political development is ethnicity. For Balewa, this ubiquitous factor intrudes in a great many situations because Nigerian societies are made up of many ethnic groups of various sizes and influence. These imply that groups are distinct from each other on the basis of language, social organization and other cultural characteristics. Adamu (1999) also noted that "No two people can walk together except they agree, and no two people can ever agree except they understand themselves". Thus the absence of consensus within these diverse groups before merging undoubtedly exacerbates conflict with high level of immobilism. The amalgamation policy denied the different ethnic groups in Nigeria the right to basic need of participation, equality and social wellbeing thereby creating ethnic cleavage. The effects of amalgamation were numerous. First, colonialism through indirect rule policy fostered ethnic cleavage between majority and minority groups by creating a largely artificial regions with each region containing a majority group that dominate in it: the Hausa/ Fulani in the North, the Yoruba's in the West and Igbos in the East resulting to fermentation of

what Weiner in 1993 called “*the development of a mono-ethnic tendency*”.

Secondly with regional system of government these major ethnic groups became the political elites that were in control of the affairs of the state, as major political parties that emerged to control each regions were political elites from these major ethnic groups. The three major political parties that came up at independence were regional ethnic parties: Northern people congress (NPC) in the North, the National Council of Nigerian Citizen (NCNC) in the East, the Action Group (AG) in the West. In reality the Hausa/Fulani, Yoruba and the Igbos formed the first political parties before independence and the minority ethnic groups were silence in political participation.

Nevertheless these political parties were all intents and purpose, sectional parties political parties which could have acted as agents of national development became champions of interest and particularism of the major ethnic groups. The more these political parties struggle and fight among themselves because of ethnicity, the more it becomes difficult for the federal government to achieve any meaningful economic and political development. The mentality which indirect rule system created encouraged the fractionalization of ethnic groups in Nigeria and these has in turn reinforced ethnic conflicts as these sentiments were often aroused in the competition for power, material resources and privileges. Political participation often degenerates into an unrelenting war to acquire defend or gain access to state power. As Ebegbulem (2010) aptly observed, the politics of ethnic and regional security play a key role in Nigeria's political and economic development as well as its role in Africa. This is because ethnicity is the major source of growing political crisis in Nigeria. Ethnicity undermines the proper selection of responsible national leadership by politicizing ethnicity. In Nigeria, national leaders are recruited on the basis of ethnicity, not experience and vision thus Nigeria's political and economic growth falls below comparison with other countries. The prevalence of ethnicity in political arena has resulted in periodic outbreaks of ethnic violence between different ethnic groups in Nigeria (Ebegbulem, 2010).

The indirect rule system contributed greatly in politicizing ethnicity which is detrimental to national unity and socio economic well-being. It was argued that indirect rule policy was used by colonialists to create inter-ethnic war thereby capitalizing on the isolation of ethnic groups and also to pitch on ethnic groups against each other thus hindering unity among them. Ethnicity was also used by colonialists in the distribution of economic resources to favour a particular ethnic group pushing marginalized groups to use their ethnic front to mobilize for equality; these often result to conflicts. The indirect rule was not the appropriate mechanism for managing tribal animosity in the country, Coleman in 1958 opined that, rather it only reinforced ethnic divisions; it complicated the task of welding diverse elements into a Nigerian nation.

Suffice it to say, the injuries which ethnic conflicts created in Nigeria's political atmosphere contributed greatly to the demise of the first republic and subsequent military regime of General Ironsi in 1966. It was argued by Dare in 1984 that the military regime of Ironsi was short lived because of ethnicity. The Hausa/Fulani ethnic group in the North saw it as a means of dislodging the Northern hegemony from power and the imposition of a southerner particularly Ibo domination over the whole Nigeria. These ethnic sentiments provided an inroad to the May riots and the massacre of Ibos in the North points to incontestable facts into the problems of ethnic conflicts in Nigeria as an impediment to

political and economic development.

RELIGIOUS DIVISION

There is no denying the fact that religion plays a very significant role in the unification of any group in the society and the world in general. It determines the way of life of any group in terms of culture, character and belief system. Religion defines what is perceived as beautiful and ugly, right and wrong, good and bad in the eyes of its followers. Thus religion, culture and ethnicity are inter-woven in any given situation. Edward Tylor's position of 1871 adds credence to this when he asserted culture as the way of life of people which implies that, as a way, people's life is reflected in their beliefs, religion and behaviour involving, language, dressing, dancing, music and food. As I have occasion to point out that apart from culture, religion and ethnicity are like twins, babies although not conceived at the same time but can be used interchangeably to actualize negative and positive purposes in any sociological situations. This is because both religion and ethnicity enforce each other at one point, and are antagonistic in another situation.

As Crawford Young noted in 1979 that religion offers both a comprehensive world view and an all-embracing social identity, so does ethnicity or religious beliefs will also mostly hold similar attitudes and opinions and individuals will behave in a similar way toward each other in social relations than others? These imply that, people seem to identify their collective conscience, morality and collective representation through religion. Studies carried out by various scholars spanning the period from the 1950s till date serve to show that severally religion has a deleterious effect on politics and the general wellbeing of Nigeria. In a developing nation like Nigeria, religion is used as a springboard for ethnic identification. Insofar as politics and governance is concerned, religion plays a key role in political bargaining and the struggle for control of state affairs. The aftermath of the 1914 amalgamation policy generated a lot of ethnic tension that has invariably hindered the economic and political development and is still haunting Nigeria in contemporary times.

The most deliberate act was the confinement of two different religious entities together under one national umbrella and political authority. The merging of Christianity and Islamic religion to a distinct geographical setting called Nigeria with their accompanying differences, prejudices and biases resulted to ethno-religious conflicts and to what Huntington in 1968 called *it accident of geography and colonialism*. These imply that Nigeria's state encompassing many religious, ethnic and linguistic groups. Dare in 1986 reported that, the elites who mounted the political ladder at independence in 1960, and whose duty it was to shape and develop the future of their country became undoubtedly tribal-centred, whose politics were conditioned by primordial and religious interest.

In considering religious identity and solidarity ties as instruments of political bargaining, the elite class of the various ethnic groups in Nigeria engage in constant struggle for the control of state power and when they gain political power they use it to perpetuate and ensure the dominance of members of their own ethnic and religious groups in the nation's bureaucratic setting. These create a situation of conflict among religious groups and also the minority groups struggle for recognition in the distribution of national resources. Religious division has really affected the development of the civil service, it undermines the Weberian

precepts of universalistic orientation based on achieved rather than ascribed norms or particularism thus, distorted the effectiveness and efficiency of the public service. The implications of these is that instead of employing people based on proper qualification or experience rather emphasis is placed on religious affiliation as a basis for employment. In the very words of Margaret Peli in 1976 stated that with “Christianity and Islam” taking centre stage as a multi religious country, the influence of religion has been rather pervasive for quite a long time.

The impact of religious division on employment issues

For instance, between 1954 to 1966 in Northern region: religious division prevented the TIVS ethnic groups in particular and other Non-Hausa Fulani minorities in the Northern region from having access or employment into civil service because of their religious differences, culture and political disparity between the ruling party in the North (NPC). In recent times, national politics in Nigeria has been clouded with religious sentiments both in appointment into federal ministries and allocation of resources within the various federating units in the country and these ugly scenarios is not compatible with economic development. The advent of military into the political sphere worsen, the incidence of religious division in Nigeria as one military regime supplanted the other from 1966 to 1999 all from the same ethnic and religious background. The present civilian administration of President Buhari, the incidence of religious division escalated as majority of the federal appointment of ministers in the federal executive council were mostly members from Hausa/Fulani ethnic and religious group. Politicizing religious division is rather devastating on Nigeria's political and economic development.

CIVIL WAR, MILITANCY AND TERRORISM

The ascendancy of amalgamation policy of 1914 resulting to the unification of Northern and Southern protectorates undoubtedly remain one of the most controversial and contentious issues in contemporary Nigerian federation. More than a 100 years after this policy was introduced. The aftermath consequences of this policy euphoria have made political scientists, sociologists, anthropologists and political activists in considering whether the 1914 amalgamation policy by British colonialism was a curse or blessing to Nigeria as a nation. This is because up till now, Nigeria's political elites are still trying to grapple with the appropriate mechanism on how to manage the crisis and mutual paranoia between the north and south that has generated a lot of insecurity and instability that resulted to the demise of the first republic and military coup in 1966 was orchestrated by ethnicity via amalgamation policy.

The first military coup of January 1966 and subsequent counter coup became obvious to all observers in Nigeria that the civilian regime of the first republic and founding fathers had failed in its primary functions of maintaining law and order and national integration that would have promoted economic and political development in the nation. This is because the political elites in the first republic were uncoordinated in the management of ethnic crisis that polarize the country based on north-south dichotomy. The military coup that brought General Ironsi as the head of state became a bad omen to the northern elements; they saw the military coup as being motivated by ethnicity and sectionalism.

As Dare in 1986 aptly noted, the northerners saw the military regime of Ironsi as a way

of dislodging the Hausa/Fulani hegemony from the control of state powers and also as a means of imposing a southerner particularly Ibo ethnic group domination over the whole Nigeria. The Promulgation of unification decree by General Ironsi administration aimed at building national integration deepened inter-ethnic suspicion and these led to the massacre of Ibos both in the military and civilians officers resident in the northern region. Unlike the January coup of 1966 which happened simultaneously in Lagos, Kaduna and Ibadan. The counter coup of July 1966 showed a lack of formal plan but rather the desperation of the northerners in overthrowing the Ibos and southern hegemony from the control of the state. The assassination of General Ironsi and his associates mostly Ibos points to the fact that politics and ethnicity had already infiltrated the military. These twin factors escalated crisis that almost disrupted national integration and security. Although it was argued that, original plan of the Northern coup plotters was to take the North out of the federation.

The history of Nigeria from this point was that of slow and inevitable degeneration towards a thirty month civil war between 1967 to 1970 couple with the annulment of the presidential election of June 12, 1993 and the ensuing political crisis it generated plus the crisis over sharia law in the year 2000 against the spirit of the 1999 constitution. The precursor of militancy in the Niger Delta also heightens ethnic tension. This is because, the Niger Delta region felt marginalized, neglected and their environment despoiled by oil activities with severe ramifications for her economy. Besides being the kitchen of the nation thus lacks modernity which absence exacerbates issues though ossified thus generated violent protests in the region. Again the political rife between contending power forces in the Northern region resulted to the incidence of Boko-Haram terrorism. The violence of Boko Haram has left over 40,000 people dead since 2009 to 2022. The insurgency of Boko Haram in the North East of Nigeria is the biggest and most pressing challenge facing Nigeria at present.

According to Famuyiwa (2014) since 2009 precisely till date, Boko Haram insurgence in the nation resulted to a several cases of bomb blasts and thousands of death and many people injured or maimed for life, properties worth billions of naira destroyed and several thousand people displaced from their abodes. The foregoing factor represents one of the many attempts to repeal the 1914 amalgamation as being a curse than blessing to Nigeria. It should also be noted that conflicts is bound to arise considering the nature and manner in which the three geographical regions now called Nigeria was merged by British imperialism through amalgamation.

CONCLUSION

There is no gainsaying the fact that this research paper have attempted a critical assessment of how the events discussed above have through ethnicity, unequal derivation sharing formula, religious division, civil war, military and terrorism affected the economic and political development of Nigeria. It is also important to note that amalgamation of 1914 which introduced indirect rule affected the establishment of procedures and routinization of mechanism that would have ushered Nigeria into the pedestine of economic and political development. The events mentioned in this paper have directly or indirectly created a sectional, ethnic consciousness mental virus within the political elites of the three major ethnic groups till date. Essentially, no country can achieve any meaningful development in an

environment that is engulfed with crises. Conflict is not compatible with economic and political development. The struggle for power in the first republic which degenerated into armed struggle was both a reflection of the fact that the established channels for competition was wrongly laid by our colonial masters and was not properly understood by the political gladiators and also to prove that the structures which had been hurriedly setup in the twilight sleep of expiring colonialism did not take precedence. The resort to armed confrontation like the military coup and counter coup of 1966 became logical in a game without accepted rules. In such a game, the professional in the management of violence tend to win.

The years since Nigeria's independence to the present democratic dispensation can be viewed against the struggle for power and attempts at building an effective national integration and equitable distribution of national resources among the various ethnic groups within the federation which has always been compounded by crisis mostly within the minority ethnic groups. Suffice it to say that, no nation ever solves all her problems mostly in a multi-ethnic, plural or federal society. The issue of economic and political development are measured on the basis of how many of the vital problems a society is able to contain. In a developing nation particularly Nigeria, the problems of national unity takes precedence over all others. Sadly enough, political elites in Nigeria have resorted in adopting the various factors of ethnicity, sectionalism, religious division mentality in the performance of their duties against their loyalties to the state. Finally, it is asserted here by way of conclusion that, the various factors mentioned in this paper contributed greatly in the under development of Nigeria's political and economic institutions, more so the in glorious years of colonialism and military rule also resulted to growth without development in Nigerian because of amalgamation.

REFERENCES

- Alanana, O. O. (2006) *Sociology of Development*. Kaduna: Joyce Graphic Printer and Publisher.
- Adamu, H. (1999) "The state of Education in Northern Nigeria: What role or the Private Sector? Today Newspaper: December 19-25
- Burnell, P. (2011) "Political Development" retrieved from <http://www.answers.com/topic/political-development>.
- Balewa. B. A. T. (1994) *Governing Nigeria: History, Problems and Prospects*. Lagos: Malthouse press Ltd.
- Dare, L. (1986) *Political change in Nigeria: all quoted in Atonja and peace social change in Nigeria (1986)*.
- Ebegbulem; J. (2010). *Government and politics of the Modern State*: Kingsview publishing house, Calabar.
- Coleman (1958), quoted in Ebegbulem (2010) *Government and Politics of the Modern State*: Kingsview publishing House, Calabar.
- Fashina, O. (1998) "Reflections on the National questions" in Omotayo Olorode, Wumi Raji, Titi Ogonye and Tunde Oladunjoye (eds). *Kensaro wiwa and the crises of the Nigerian state*. CPHR; Lagos.
- Famuyiwa, S. (2014). *The issue of terrorism and insecurity in Nigeria a case study of Nigerian Army*. An unpublished B.Sc thesis to the Department of Criminology and social work, faculty of management and social sciences, Adekunle Ajasin University, Ondo state,

Nigeria.

Huntington, S. (1968) *Political Order in Changing Societies*. Yale Univ, Press, New Haven, Conn.

Peli, M. (1976) *Nigerian Politics: The people's view*, London: Cassel and Company Limited.

Yonna, C. (1970, 1993) *The Politics of Cultural Pluralism*. Madison Wisconsin university o Wisconsin Press.

Park, H. S. (1984) "Human needs and political development. A dissent to utopian solution"

Retrieved from <http://www.d.umm.edu/schi/ton/articles/GPD5.html>.

Taylor, E. (1871) *Primitive Culture*.